

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Videoin B and its Stereoisomers as Inhibitors of Nipah Virus- An *In-silico* Study of Structure-Based Virtual Screening and Comparative ADMET Profiling

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Abstract

Nipah virus (NiV) can cause a pandemic. Since there are no effective treatments available for NiV, the development of drugs requires immediate attention. In the context of drug discovery, natural products have emerged as a promising branch with tremendous scope. In this study, we screened 959 phytochemicals from 10 Indian medicinal plants using the IMPPAT database, PyRx, ProTox 3.0, SwissADME and AutoDock 4. Videoin B (L2) bypassed all 7 screening levels. Its stereoisomeric forms (1R,2R,4aS,6S,8aS)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate (L1) and (1S,2S,4aR,6R,8aR)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate (L3) were obtained from the LOTUS database. L1, L2 and L3 showed binding score of -6.7, -7.5 and -7.8 kcal/mol respectively, better than the standard- Ribavirin (L0) when docked with the attachment glycoprotein of NiV. The impact of stereoisomerism on inhibitory action, drug-like properties, ADMET profiles, and toxicology was thoroughly examined by using ADMETlab. Better docking scores, improved pharmacokinetics, medicinal properties, ADMET profiles and reduced toxicity concerns suggest that these three natural products- L1, L2 and L3 can be potent candidates for the novel drug discovery of Niv. Hence, this study is a step towards pandemic preparedness and aims to contribute to the drug development of deadly NiV.

Keywords: Nipah Virus; *In-Silico* Analysis; Structure-Based Virtual Screening; Stereoisomers; Docking; ADMET

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Graphical Abstract

1. Introduction

Nipah virus (NiV) belongs to genus *henipavirus*, family Paramyxoviridae and order Mononegaviruses (1–4). It is a highly pathogenic, zoonotic virus (5). It is enveloped, has negative-sense single-stranded RNA and is considered a pathogen corresponding to biosafety level 4, hence needing utmost care in laboratory handling (2,6,7). Pteropid fruit bats, also called as flying foxes, are primarily the natural reservoir of NiV (2,6,8–12). Their excreta and saliva help in transmitting the virus and causing disease to secondary hosts/intermediate hosts (domestic animals like pigs, goats, horses, etc.), which in turn spread infection in humans when consumed (5,13). Humans and animals can develop the disease by eating bat-bitten dates or other fruits. The viral envelope has the attachment G and fusion F protein responsible for its entry into the host cell (11,14). Broad-spectrum antivirals like Ribavirin, Remdesivir and Flavipiravir are used in the treatment of NiV (3,4,15). NiV infections lead to inflammation of the brain, causing encephalitis and eventually death (2,15). Since it has high death rates, researchers are in desperate search of an effective medication, for which natural products can turn out to be a good option. In the context of drug discovery, this branch has limited exploration and tremendous scope. Direct lab exploration is immensely time and resource-consuming; hence, in-silico approaches are used to bridge this gap and save time and resources.

Figure 1 Global impact and percent mortality rate of NiV

Countries in which NiV spread has been reported are Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, India and Bangladesh (16–18). Global impact has been shown in Fig. 1, which gives the mortality rate from year 1998 to 2023 for each country. The first outbreak was in Malaysia in 1998 with a 40% mortality rate, followed by Singapore in 1999 with a mortality rate as low as 9%. Similarly, there was only one outbreak in Philippines in 2014. Bangladesh had the maximum number of cases with a considerably high fatality rate, almost every year. India comes second in the list, but the outbreak was not observed regularly, as seen in the case of Bangladesh. In 2021, India had a 100% mortality rate. In India, the first outbreak was in Siliguri City (West Bengal) in 2001 (1,6). There are 2 strains of this virus- Bangladeshi and Malaysian, the former being more virulent than the latter because it shows human-to-human transmission and is circulated in India due to close geographical proximity. This virus is currently restricted to certain regions, but it is capable of causing a pandemic (2).

Natural products (NPs) and their derivatives show good results in clinical trials as effective drugs because they exhibit less toxicity as compared to synthetic drugs (19–21). Well-known anti-inflammatory drug acetylsalicylic acid, derived from *Salix alba* plant's active component, is one of the most successful drugs marketed (22,23). Another such example is *Colchicine* from *Colchicum autumnale*, used for gout and various other inflammatory diseases (22,24). For COVID-19, Virofree was reported to fight SARS-CoV-2 infection (22). Furthermore, NPs used for COVID-19, like *Myricetin* (25,26), *Punicalagin* (26,27), *Gallinamide A* (26,28), have been reported. Few studied phytochemicals exhibiting Anti-HIV activity are *Daphneodorins A & B* (26,29), *Kleinhospitine E* (26,30), *Beesioside* (26,31). Anticancer agents have been developed by the U.S. National Cancer Institute with the help of NPs (32). Whereas *Bifucatriol* (26,33), *Kakeromamide* (26,34), *Halymeniaol* (26,35) are Anti-malarial agents obtained from plants. A few more reported compounds are *Ubonodin* (36), *Santacruzamate A* (26,37), *Honaucin A* (26,38,39). Automation can extensively and rapidly screen vast chemical libraries virtually against biological targets, speed up the drug discovery procedures (22,39–42).

In the present research, we aim to identify potential inhibitors of the attachment-G protein of NiV by virtually screening 959 phytochemicals present in 10 Indian medicinal plants, namely Patala (*Stereospermum suaveolens*), Shalaparni (*Desmodium gangeticum*), Musta (*Cyperus rotundus*), Chirayata (*Swertia chirata*), Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*), Bhunimba (*Andrographis paniculata*), Patha (*Cissampelos pareira*), Vasaka (*Justicia adhatoda*), Agnimantha (*Clerodendrum phlomidis*) and Nirgundi (*Vitex negundo*). Vitedoin B and its stereoisomeric forms- (1R,2R,4aS,6S,8aS)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate and (1S,2S,4aR,6R,8aR)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate were thoroughly studied to analyse the impact of stereoisomerism on inhibiting activity, binding affinity, pharmacokinetics, ADMET profiles and toxicology of all these NiV attachment glycoprotein-inhibiting molecules.

2. Methods

2.1. Protein structure retrieval, quality assessment and structural validation.

With careful consideration of various important parameters, the best structure of attachment glycoprotein of NiV came out to be 2VWD.

The structure of the attachment glycoprotein- G (2VWD) given in Fig. 2 was obtained from RCSB PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) Protein Data Bank, which is a well-known database containing structures of different proteins in different forms (43–45). The structure was downloaded in PDB format, available amongst the various download options. The PDB DOI of the chosen protein is <https://doi.org/10.2210/pdb2VWD/pdb>. The 3D structure verification and quality assessment were done using the ERRAT score (46), Verify3D (<https://www.doe-mbi.ucla.edu/verify3d/>) (47) and Ramachandran plot from Discovery Studio Visualizer(48).

Figure 2 3D structure of the attachment glycoprotein (PDB ID: 2VWD) of Niva

2.2. Standard & Ligands structure retrieval.

Ribavirin, a broad-spectrum antiviral, was taken as the standard. Its structure was obtained from the PubChem database (<https://PubChem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) managed by the U.S National Institutes of Health (NIH) in SDF format, which was later converted to PDB and PDBQT format for docking. Structures of all phytochemicals present in 10 Indian medicinal plants were taken from the IMPPAT database (<https://cb.imsc.res.in/imppat/>). A similar structure search was done on PubChem. Stereoisomeric structures were obtained from the LOTUS database (<https://lotus.naturalproducts.net/>) (49). The molecular formula of all three ligands is $C_{19}H_{30}O_4$. Table 1 enlists the PubChem ID/ LOTUS ID, canonical smiles and the structures of the standard and ligand.

2.3. Docking

Initially, the protein preparation was done in UCSF ChimeraX 1.8 by removing all non-standard residues to remove the non-proteinous part and adding missing atoms, polar hydrogen and charges. Multiple docking for all phytochemicals with the druggable target (2VWD) was done in PyRx in 3 batches, having varied numbers of ligands. Later, L0, L1, L2 and L3 were docked with 2VWD in AutoDock 4 individually. After docking, binding affinities for the best binding pose of the ligand were tabulated in an Excel sheet. The output files generated contained the binding affinity of the top 9 poses, RMSD lower and upper bound and were saved as CSV files, which were further used for analysis.

2.4. ADMET Profiling

Initially, ProTox 3.0 (<https://tox.charite.de/protox3/>) software was used to know the toxicity classes of the phytochemicals and SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) was used to check the ADME profiles of the phytochemicals during the screening stage. L1, L2 and L3 showed better binding scores and ADMET profiles than the standard-L0. hence, detailed ADMET- absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity profiling of L1, L2 and

L3 was done in comparison with L0 with the help of ADMETlab (<https://admetmesh.scbdd.com/>). ADMETlab gave a detailed and complete analysis of all ADMET parameters(50).

Table 1 Ligands, their structures, IDs and canonical smiles

	Ligand	Canonical Smiles	PubChem ID/ LOTUS ID	Structures
L0	Ribavirin (Standard)	<chem>OC[C@H]1O[C@H]([C@@H]([C@@H]1O)O)n1cnc(n1)C(=O)N</chem>	37542	
L1	(1R,2R,4aS,6S,8aS)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate	<chem>CC(=O)O[C@H]1CC[C@@]2(C)[C@@H](CC[C@@H](C)[C@]23CC(=O)O3)C1(C)C</chem>	Q105025374	
L2	2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate	<chem>CC(=O)OC1CCC2(C)C(CCC(C)C23CCC(=O)O3)C1(C)C</chem>	Q105025375	
L3	(1S,2S,4aR,6R,8aR)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate	<chem>CC(=O)O[C@@H]1CC[C@]2(C)[C@@H](CC[C@H](C)[C@@]23CCC(=O)O3)C1(C)C</chem>	Q105025376	

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Structural validation and quality assessment of 2VWD

Ramachandran plot and Verify3D along with ERRAT score were used to assess the overall structural quality of the protein(51,52). Fig. 3 shows the Ramachandran plot with a high majority of protein residues in the most favoured region indicated by green, which is a very positive sign indicating that the protein's structure is energetically stable and well-defined. Very few points are in red, that is the disallowed region. Some of the residues in this region might be acceptable if they belong to flexible loops. The overall quality of the protein structure is good as suggested by the Ramachandran plot obtained from Discovery Studio Visualizer.

Figure 3 Ramachandran plot of the attachment glycoprotein of NiV (PDB ID- 2VWD)

Verify3D plot is used to check if the 3D structure of the protein complies with the 1D sequence and if the amino acid residues are in an energetically favoured environment(48,53). Positive values indicate a favourable environment, whereas negative values don't. A large majority of the scores for the residues are positive, as seen in Fig. 4, suggesting that the overall fold of the protein shows consistency with its 1D sequence, meaning they have a higher 3D-1D score. Although there are certain dips below zero, the overall quality of the protein structure based on sequence is good since 80.92% of the amino acids have the same 3D environment as suggested by the sequence, because they scored above 0.1, which is considered the threshold of acceptability. Thus, the verify3D plot also suggests that the protein structure meets the criteria for a good quality protein and hence, can be taken ahead for further studies. Lastly, on ERRAT, the protein structure was run and the overall quality factor of the protein structure was 93.4949 out of 100, indicating very high-quality protein.

Figure 4 Verify3D plot for chain A and B of the attachment glycoprotein of NiV (PDB ID- 2VWD)

3.2. Virtual Screening

For 10 Indian medicinal plants, namely Patala (*Stereospermum suaveolens*), Shalaparni (*Desmodium gangeticum*), Musta (*Cyperus rotundus*), Chirayata (*Swertia chirata*), Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*), Bhunimba (*Andrographis paniculata*), Patha (*Cissampelos pareira*), Vasaka (*Justicia adhatoda*), Agnimantha (*Clerodendrum phlomidis*) and Nirgundi (*Vitex negundo*), 959 phytochemicals were listed down from the IMPPAT database. Post elimination of duplicates, 470 remained. Docking of all these 470 phytochemicals and the standard was done with the Attachment Glycoprotein (2VWD) of Nipah virus. Results obtained from docking showed that out of these 470, 180 demonstrated better binding affinity than the standard-Ribavirin, which showed binding affinity = -6.6 kcal/mol. The toxicity classes of all these compounds were checked using ProTox-3.0 software. Compounds with toxicity classes 5 and 6 were screened out. 32 such compounds were found, out of which 27 were blood-brain barrier permeant, not a P-gp substrate and were drug-like. Only 2 did not inhibit the CYP450 enzymes. Lastly, only 1 compound, Videoin B (L2), complied with the original docking score on redocking individually, while the other did not. These 7 levels of screening are shown in Fig. 5. Hence, for Vitedoin B similar structure search was done with the help of PubChem and LOTUS databases, resulting in the selection of L1 and L3 as 2 non-planar stereoisomers of L2

Figure 5 Various stages of Virtual Screening for Niv Lead Compound discovery

3.3. Docking results analysis

Figure 6 Best docked posed of L0, L1, L2 and L3 with protein 2VWD

3.3.1. Quantitative and comparative data analysis of binding affinities

Table 2 enlists the binding score, type of interactions between the ligand and the interacting amino acid residues and the binding site in which L0, L1, L2 and L3 are present. Fig. 6 shows the ligands bound in the binding pockets of the protein-2VWD, an enlarged view of the binding site and the 2D diagram showing different interactions present in the protein-ligand complex formation. L0 has a binding affinity of - 6.6 kcal/mol. L1 has a binding affinity - 6.7 kcal/mol. There is a difference of -0.1 units in the binding affinities of L0 and L1. L2 and L3 show significantly higher negative values of binding affinity than L0. L2 exhibits -7.5 and L3 shows -7.8 kcal/mol.

Table 2 Binding affinities, interaction types and binding site coordinates for protein in complexation with L0, L1, L2 and L3

Protein complexed with	Binding affinity (in kcal/mol)	Type of interactions	Binding site coordinates (x, y, z)
L0	-6.6	Unfavourable donor-donor Van der Waals Conventional hydrogen Carbon hydrogen Pi-cation Pi-donor hydrogen Pi-alkyl	-47.006413, -9.721968, -24.949323
L1	-6.7	Van der Waals Conventional hydrogen	-42.043783, -1.941174, -16.125174
L2	-7.5	Van der Waals Conventional hydrogen	-14.592783, -29.771478, -25.868087
L3	-7.8	Van der Waals Conventional hydrogen Carbon hydrogen	-41.927783, -1.905391, -16.008435

3.3.2. Structural differences and their impact

Figure 7 Common 2D diagram for L1, L2 and L3 with stereocenters

Three important key parameters affecting the binding affinity are planarity, stereochemistry and binding site coordinates. As seen in Table 2, L1, L2 and L3 share the same molecular formula $C_{19}H_{30}O_4$ and the same atom connectivity, but they have different spatial arrangements. Since all stereoisomers have different 3D diagrams but share the same 2D diagram, in Fig. 7, the Common 2D diagram for L1, L2, and L3 has been given with their stereocenters highlighted in green. There are 5 stereocenters for L1, L2 and L3 as mentioned in Table 3 and seen in Fig. 7. In L2, all the groups at the stereocenters lie in the plane of the paper, hence it demonstrates a planar structure, limiting its interactions to chain A of 2VWD. The 5 stereocenters in L1, L2, and L3 are C-1, C-2, C-4a, C-6 and C-8a where C1 is the spiro carbon atom connecting the naphthalene ring to the oxolan ring; C2 is the carbon atom bearing the methyl group on the naphthalene ring; C4a is the bridgehead carbon atom present between the two rings of the naphthalene; C6 bears the acetate group on the naphthalene ring and C8a again is the bridgehead carbon but it bears the methyl group on the naphthalene ring. For L1, stereochemistry is 1R,2R,4aS,6S,8aS as indicated by the name of the compound in Table 1. If 1R becomes 1S, 2R becomes 2S, 4aS becomes 4aR, 6S becomes 6R and 8aS becomes 8aR, that is, if the stereochemistry at the stereocenters of L1 is inverted, the resulting compound would be L3. Therefore, L1 and L3 are non-planar

structures, due to which they can access a binding site that is present between chain A and chain B. Thus, differences in the planarity directly influence the interaction profiles and the available binding pockets. Changing the stereochemistry of specific groups causes a difference of -1.1 units in the docking score, which highlights the sensitivity of binding affinity to minor stereochemical changes. The binding site coordinates for L1 and L3 are proximate. However, they still differ due to their distinct 3D conformation. This enables L1 and L3 to interact with different amino acid residues in chains A and B. Changes in stereochemistry alter the ability of the ligands to interact with the same set of residues, thus affecting binding affinity.

3.3.3. Correlation between interactions and the binding affinity

Conventional hydrogen bonds are important for improving the binding score. All three stereoisomers L1, L2 and L3 exhibit at least one conventional hydrogen bonding, due to which they have improved docking scores compared to L0, which displays an unfavorable interaction.

L3 has a unique feature compared to its other stereoisomers; it has an additional carbon-hydrogen bond present and hence has the best docking score. Carbon-hydrogen bond is a significant score-enhancing interaction. This additional feature enhances the docking score and makes L3 the most potent binder, having the highest negative value of binding affinity. Van der Waals interactions are present in all four ligands L0, L1, L2 and L3

L1 shows 14 Van der Waals interactions. L2 and L3 show 13 interactions. Although these interactions contribute less significantly to the docking score, the combined effect of numerous such interactions shows a significant impact in a positive manner. Hence, all the stereoisomers present better scores than the standard.

3.4. ADMET predictions

Table 3 ADMET predictions of L0, L1, L2 and L3

PARAMETERS UNDER EVALUATION		LIGANDS			
		L0	L1	L2	L3
Physicochemical properties	Molecular weight	244.08	322.21	32.21	32.21
	nHA	9	4	4	4
	nHD	5	0	0	0
	nRot	3	2	2	2
	nRing	2	3	3	3
	nHet	9	4	4	4
	fChar	0	0	0	0
	nRig	11	18	18	18
	Flexibility	0.273	0.111	0.111	0.111
	Stereocenters	4	5	5	5
TPSA	143.72	52.6	52.6	52.6	
Medicinal chemistry	QED	0.443	0.688	0.688	0.688
	SAScore	3.869	4.564	4.564	4.564
	Fsp3	0.625	0.895	0.895	0.895
	NPscore	0.691	3.128	3.128	3.128
	Lipinski rule	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	GSK rule	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	Golden triangle	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	Colloidal aggregations	0.058	0.536	0.104	0.576

	Ghose rule	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Veber rule	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Egan rule	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Muegge rule	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Absorption	Caco-2 Permeability update	-5.656	-4.696	-4.776	-4.784
	Pgp substrate	0.675	0.0	0.0	0.0
Distribution	PPB	15.11%	68.01%	86.92%	92.36%
	VDss	22.122	0.618	0.954	1.51
	BBB penetration	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Fu	83.61%	32.28%	17.26%	15.13%
Metabolism	CYP450	None	None	None	None
	GI absorption	Low	High	High	High
Excretion	CLplasma	4.206	6.367	4.444	7.947
	T1/2	0.721	0.263	0.232	0.166
Toxicity	Neurotoxicity	0.554	0.097	0.607	0.33
	Ototoxicity	0.897	0.175	0.43	0.281
	Hematotoxicity	0.647	0.524	0.254	0.389
	Nephrotoxicity	0.58	0.755	0.339	0.409
	Genotoxicity	0.996	0.476	0.019	0.752
	Immunotoxicity	0.069	0.026	0.047	0.051
	A549 cytotoxicity	0.021	0.115	0.086	0.121
	hERG blockers	0.018	0.049	0.036	0.014
	Hepatotoxicity	0.777	0.548	0.424	0.566
	DILI	0.983	0.558	0.475	0.344
	AMES toxicity	0.806	0.523	0.254	0.516
	Rat oral acute toxicity	0.01	0.109	0.098	0.053
	Carcinogenicity	0.183	0.305	0.07	0.041
	Eye irritation	0.134	0.984	0.558	0.043
	Respiratory toxicity	0.017	0.953	0.863	0.406
	Acute toxicity rule	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts
	Genotoxic Carcinogenicity Rule	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts
	NonGenotoxic Carcinogenicity Rule	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts
	Skin Sensitization Rule	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts
	Aquatic Toxicity Rule	0 alerts	2 alerts	2 alerts	2 alerts
	NonBiodegradable Rule	1 alert	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts
	SureChEMBL Rule	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts	0 alerts

Table 3 gives us detailed information about the physicochemical properties, medicinal chemistry and ADMET parameters for thorough theoretical evaluation.

3.4.1. Physicochemical property

Physicochemical properties are physical and chemical properties of a substance describing how it might behave based on its structure and composition (54–59). The physicochemical properties of all the stereoisomers are the same, but they differ from those of the standard. L0 is more polar than needed. For L1, L2 and L3. Molecular weight should range between 100 to 600, based on the drug-like soft rule (60). Similarly, the number of hydrogen bond acceptors should be between 0 to 12, and the number of hydrogen bond donors should be between 0 to 7. These are also based on drug-like soft rules. The number of rotatable bonds should be in the range 0 to 11. A molecule can have a maximum of six rings. optimal formal charge ranges between -4 to +4. The number of heteroatoms can be a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 15. The maximum number of rigid bonds can be 30. Flexibility is the ratio of the number of rotatable bonds divided by the number of rigid bonds. The number of stereo centres should be equal to or less than 2, which is based on the lead-like rules. Polar fragments contribute to the surface area; the sum of the contributions of all polar fragments is known as the topological polar surface area. Its optimal range is 0 to 140.

Figure 8 Spider web diagram for physicochemical properties with upper and lower limit

The spider web diagram in Fig. 8 for L0 highlights the values for physicochemical properties in and out of the ranges. The lower limit is marked by green, and the upper limit is marked by blue. The compound's properties are marked in yellow. The three stereoisomers in the spider web diagram are seen to lie in the optimal ranges. Despite different spatial arrangements, L1, L2 and L3 exhibit identical values. LogP and LogD values for L0 are less than the lower limit, and TPSA exceeds the upper limit. LogD is LogP but a pH-dependent version of the same. If LogP and LogD are lower, it means that the drug molecule is less lipophilic and more hydrophilic. Less lipophilic molecules are unable to cross a lipid-rich barrier like the BBB. It also indicates that the L0 has poor absorption in the GI tract because of its inability to pass through intestinal linings composed of lipid membranes. Such hydrophilic molecules will be excreted from the body very quickly. Distribution in tissues rich in lipid is also significantly hindered because of low absorption. TPSA higher than the desired value indicates increased polarity, limiting the ability to pass through the BBB, a lipid-rich membrane, as stated earlier. Poor oral bioavailability is a result of hindered ability to cross the intestinal lipid made molecules. Hence, the L0 is not likely to reach the bloodstream. This raises significant concerns about the absorption, distribution and overall potency and efficacy of L0.

3.4.2. Medicinal Chemistry

QED (Quantitative Estimate of Drug-likeness) calculates 8 drug-like parameters and measures drug-likeness (61,62). For all the stereoisomers, the QED score is the same and lies in an excellent range. Synthetic accessibility score should

be between 1-10 for all molecules, 10 being the toughest to synthesize. All SA Scores are in the acceptable range. The fraction of sp³ carbon is used to find out how three-dimensional the molecule is. Generally, a higher value is considered better and means that there are more sp³ hybridized carbons. All stereoisomers have a higher value than L0. NP score should be in the range -5 to +5. A higher score indicates a higher probability of being a natural product. The NP scores indicate that all stereoisomers are natural products, while the standard is not. The Lipinski rule of 5 is followed by all the ligands. Compounds satisfying the GSK rule and the golden triangle rule are predicted to have a more favorable ADMET profile. All stereoisomers are seen to follow the commonly employed rules like Ghose, Veber, Egan and Muegge, but L0 does not adhere to these rules. This is an indication of good oral absorption, reasonable bioavailability and fewer ADME issues. Formation of colloidal aggregates is not desirable because it prevents the molecule from binding to the surface of the desired disease-causing protein. L0 has the least possibility, and L2 has an extremely small score for the formation of aggregate colloidal amongst all stereoisomers.

3.4.3. Absorption

Absorption measures how a drug travels from the site of administration to the site of action (63). A drug which is administered orally has to pass through the intestinal cells either by passive diffusion or active transport processes or carrier-mediated uptake (64). The human colon adenocarcinoma cell lines are studied to estimate the permeability of the drug in in-vivo analysis. A value above 5.15 is generally considered good. The values in the table indicate that the standard is a PGP substrate; that is, it will be pumped out of the cell limiting its efficacy.

3.4.4. Distribution

Drug distribution refers to how drugs move through various tissues of the body and the amount of drugs in the tissues (65). Plasma protein binding (PPB) directly affects oral bioavailability because if the drug binds to the plasma protein, its concentration in the free state is at stake, hence, its value should be less than 90% (66). The standard-L0 has the lowest PPB percent. L1 and L2 show plasma binding less than 90% conversely, L3 shows 92.36% PPB. Thus, due to a change in the stereochemistry, there is a severe impact on the therapeutic index. L3 has the least therapeutic index due to the highest plasma protein binding, and L1 has a better therapeutic index than L2. VD_{ss} is the volume of distribution at steady state, it is a measure of effective distribution of the drug molecule throughout the body (67,68). A lower value is considered favourable because a higher value indicates the probability of unpredictable distribution. The standard comparatively has the highest value. The values are very low for the stereoisomers. L0 is not permeable through the blood-brain-barrier; on the other hand, L1, L2 and L3 are, which is also seen in the BoiledEGG Model given in Fig. 9. Fraction unbound plasma percent (Fu%) should be higher, indicating a high concentration of drug in the free state available for binding with the desired protein site (69,70). The standard shows a higher Fu%, whereas the three stereoisomers exhibit a low percentage.

3.4.5. Metabolism

Drug metabolism measures the drug's action intensity and how it is broken down by the enzymes. CYP450 enzymes are a set of enzymes present in the liver responsible for breaking down drug molecules. Their activity should not be slowed down or inhibited (71-75). None of the molecules is known to inhibit these enzymes. GI Absorption of L0 is low, which means it will have poor bioavailability. L1, L2, and L3 show high absorption in the GI track, which is clearly seen in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 Boiled EGG Model for L0, L1, L2 & L3

The Boiled EGG Model given in Fig. 9 supports physicochemical results as the point for the standard lies in the outside region. This is an indication that L0 is neither BBB+ nor does it demonstrate good GI absorption. The yolk region gives us information about the ability to cross the BBB, the egg white region points to good GI absorption for drugs that are administered orally (76). These results are in good compliance with the ones tabulated in Table 3. Hence, unlike L0, they can pass through BBB, which is a very selective membrane. This is understood by the presence of their points in the yolk region of the Boiled EGG Model.

3.4.6. Excretion

Drug clearance can help determine the frequency of dosing (77–79). It is expressed in mL per minute per kilogram (mL/min/kg). L1 and L3 show moderate clearance, whereas L0 and L2 demonstrate poor clearance. $T_{1/2}$ provides information about the half-life of the drug. Drugs having small half-lives require more frequent dosing, while those with long half-lives need less frequent dosing (80,81). L0, L1, L2, and L3 all are seen to show ultra-short half-lives, since their values for half-lives are less than 1 hour, which is too small. This necessitates frequent dosages. In cases of NiV infections needing critical care, ultra-short half-lives allow precise control over the drug's effect, minimizing the risk of drug accumulation inside the body. This offers an advantage of safety, because the drug's effects can be stopped immediately if any adverse reactions occur. Drugs with ultrashort half-lives require specialized delivery methods.

3.4.7. Toxicology

L1 is least likely to exhibit neurotoxicity, while L2 is most likely to do so. L1 and L3 are not expected to exhibit neurotoxicity, whereas L0 and L2 might show moderate neurotoxicity because their values lie between 0.3 and 0.7. Neurotoxicity trend: **L1<L3<L0<L2**. L0 might cause damage to the inner ear, either by directly damaging the ear's structure or by affecting the nervous system (82–85). Ototoxicity trend: **L1<L3<L2<L0**. Adverse effects on blood-forming organs are known as hematotoxicity. L0 is most likely to demonstrate hematotoxicity. Hematotoxicity trend: **L2<L3<L0<L1**. L1, followed by L0, are more likely to affect the kidneys and cause nephrotoxicity. L0 can cause toxicity to the genes, potentially leading to cancer, while L2 is the least likely to cause genotoxicity. Genotoxicity trend: **L2<L1<L3<L0**. Results show that L0 has the highest chance of causing immunotoxicity, whereas L1 has the least chance of causing toxicity to the RPMI-8226 cell lines. Immunotoxicology: **L1<L2<L3<L0**. A549 is a human non-small cell lung cancer cell line (86–90). The probability of causing toxicity to this cell line is indicated by the trend **L0<L2<L1<L3**. If hERG is blocked, it might lead to long QT syndrome, arrhythmia, and torsades de pointes (TDP), leading to palpitations

or even sudden death (91–96). None of the ligands are hERG blockers. L0 has the highest probability of inducing liver injury (hepatotoxicity) and exhibiting drug-induced liver injury (DILI), while the three stereoisomers fall within the moderate range, suggesting they do not have issues associated with hepatotoxicity and DILI. The Ames Mutagenicity test is important as it is closely related to carcinogenicity (97–100). The predictions suggest that L0 has the highest probability of causing mutagenicity, while L2 has the least chance of causing carcinogenicity due to mutagenicity. For evaluating safety, acute toxicity in mammals is determined. All ligands show very low toxicity and are all non-carcinogenic. L0 has the least probability of irritating the eye, whereas L1 has the highest. L1 and L2 have values very close to one, which indicates that they can cause respiratory toxicity. On the other hand, L0 and L3 are non-respiratory toxicants. In all the ligands, there are zero alerts for acute toxicity, genotoxic carcinogenicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, and skin sensitization rules, meaning that no studied substructures might cause problems associated with these rules. The standard-L0 has one substructure that is not biodegradable, while the three stereoisomers have two substructures that might result in aquatic toxicity.

4. Conclusion

In this research work, the attachment glycoprotein of Nipah virus has been taken as the druggable target. L1, L2 and L3 showed binding scores of -6.7, -7.5 and -7.8 kcal/mol, respectively, better than the standard-Ribavirin (L0) when docked with the attachment glycoprotein of NiV. All 3 stereoisomers show differences in their properties due to the change in stereochemistry. This shows that stereoisomerism can have a significantly high impact on a molecule's binding energy and ADMET profile. NiV infections rapidly reach the brain, causing inflammation of the brain; hence, an effective drug that can cross the BBB and progress to the CNS is required. Ribavirin has severe toxicity issues, no permeation through the BBB, which is critical for NiV and has poor absorption in the GI tract, limiting its efficacy. L1, L2 and L3 show better properties and the ability to permeate through the BBB, better absorption and reduced toxicity problems. Hence, according to the current study, the 3 stated stereoisomers- (1R,2R,4aS,6S,8aS)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate, Vitedoin B and (1S,2S,4aR,6R,8aR)-2,5,5,8a-tetramethyl-5'-oxo-octahydro-2H-spiro[naphthalene-1,2'-oxolan]-6-yl acetate can be potent candidates in the novel drug discovery of NiV due to their improved physicochemical and medicinal properties along with considerably better and suitable ADMET profiles in context of NiV as compared to the standard - Ribavirin.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Author's Contributions

KBZS has prepared the original draft, conceptualized and visualized the study, curated the data, performed the necessary methodology and formal data analysis using all the software's, while SPP supervised and guided the whole process along providing critical reviews. DNR not only contributed to formatting and proof reading the document but also helped with troubleshooting of software's.

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